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Assessing and validating corporate low-carbon transition strategies: a comparative analysis of approaches and methodologies

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ABSTRACT

Independent assessments and validations of corporate low-carbon transition strategies offer valuable insights for investors, policymakers and other stakeholders. However, there is a limited understanding of how individual methodologies cover key policy-relevant transition components underlying their assessment outputs and methodological differences. This lack of clarity may hinder the integration of established methods into policies aimed at advancing corporate climate accountability as well as progress within the assessment field. To address this gap, this article analyses the methodological design choices of ten corporate low-carbon transition strategy assessments with publicly available methodologies and results. These include the Science Based Targets initiative and the Transition Pathways Initiative. We develop a two-part framework to compare the assessment setup and the coverage of key transition strategy components and illustrate the differences, using the assessment outcomes for a major global company. Our findings help policymakers navigate the heterogeneity in key methodological parameters, notably in component coverage, the assessment approach per strategy component and weighting. We show that no single assessment initiative provides fully up-to-date, contextualized evaluations of all transition strategy components for more than 1000 companies, noting this as a key limitation. However, composite assessments, which integrate multiple assessments as sources, are emerging to address gaps in criteria coverage while maintaining contextualized assessment for each criterion. We propose a centralized repository to track and compare assessment methodologies, supporting an understanding of methodological variances and synergies between initiatives. Finally, this article provides the foundation for further research on sector-specific methodological differences and on aligning assessment methodologies with emerging global standards.

Key policy insights

- Independent initiatives use a variety of methods to assess companies and produce important data for the governance of corporate low-carbon transition strategies.
- Regulators should adopt measures that strengthen the scale and quality of data on corporate climate strategies, leveraging methodological advancements developed by independent assessment initiatives.
- Establishing a centralized repository to track and provide public access to assessment methodologies would support their integration into regulatory frameworks.
- In the interim, composite assessments that integrate multiple data sources can enhance collaboration within the governance ecosystem and help fill assessment coverage gaps while preserving the strengths of individual methodologies.

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1 Introduction

Following the adoption of the Paris Agreement, non-state actors, especially companies, have gained prominence in the global effort to combat climate change (Krabbe et al., 2015; UNEP, 2023). This ‘all hands on deck’ approach underscores the critical role of voluntary action complementing government policies as collective efforts are necessary to achieve ambitious climate goals (Hale, 2016; Kuramochi et al., 2020). However, as corporate net-zero pledges increased dramatically over the last several years, especially around the 2021 UN Climate Conference (COP26), so has scepticism over their credibility (Coen et al., 2022; Lin, 2022; Net Zero Tracker, 2022; NewClimate Institute, 2022). Responding to this concern, United Nations Secretary-General Antonio Guterres warned against ‘slow movers, fake movers or any form of greenwashing’ (United Nations, 2022).

Responding to these concerns, a growing number of voluntary initiatives have been set up in recent years to assess the accountability and credibility of corporate low-carbon transition strategies (LCTSs) or to provide guidance and standards (Becker et al., 2024; Noels & Jachnik, 2022). These assessments guide investment decisions, support litigation and advocacy and enhance understanding of corporate climate performance. Policymakers may also use them to evaluate their own countries’ ability to achieve emission reduction targets (Rekker et al., 2021).

The literature on the longer-standing practice of corporate environmental, social and governance (ESG) assessments shows that their outcomes significantly differ across rating agencies. The divergence of ESG ratings is largely caused by the difference in ESG attributes covered and the difference in indicators used to measure the same attribute; the enhanced ESG disclosure by companies only increases the rating divergence (e.g. Berg et al., 2022; Christensen et al., 2022). The research specifically on corporate climate action, one of many ESG categories, has also shown divergence in rating outcomes across various assessment initiatives (e.g. Chmel et al., 2023; Raynaud et al., 2020). Studies have further investigated the causes of divergence, noting variables as the choice of GHG metrics, target timeframes, emissions scopes and the treatment of avoided emissions (Noels & Jachnik, 2022; Raynaud et al., 2020; Rekker et al., 2022).

However, many studies focus primarily on the alignment of emission targets with Paris-aligned pathways – only one component of a full transition strategy. The landscape of voluntary corporate climate action standards has evolved significantly in the past few years, where convergence of recommendations across many low-carbon transition components has been observed (Becker et al., 2024). There is limited scientific literature to date that conducted a detailed comparative analysis of recently published corporate low-carbon transition strategy (LCTS) assessments and their methodologies that go beyond statistical comparisons. Understanding assessment differences at the component level is important for policymakers and other stakeholders validating a 1.5°C-compatible transition plan, as headline alignment scores can mask substantive methodological divergences in how individual elements of transition strategies, such as governance, implementation plans, capital allocation or monitoring, are evaluated. Moreover, many studies are practice-oriented (Noels & Jachnik, 2022; Raynaud et al., 2020; Rekker et al., 2022), narrowly focussed on the investor community’s specific data needs and expectations that may differ from those of other stakeholders (Clément et al., 2023; Thomä et al., 2018).

Against this backdrop, this article systematically compares ten recurring, non-sector-specific LCTS assessment initiatives with public methodologies and results. Utilizing a two-part framework, we examine the differences between the assessment initiatives in the overall assessment set-up (Part I) and the individual transition strategy components (Part II). Through the two-part analysis, we aim to obtain insights into the three dimensions of LCTS assessments: breadth, LCTS’s component-level assessment approach, and frequency.

This article contributes to the literature on corporate climate action in a number of ways. First, this study advances beyond statistical comparisons to dissect and compare the specific components and methodologies of various transition assessments. Second, we examine transition strategy components beyond emissions pathways that are recognized as key to holistic assessment by policy-relevant guidance documents (ISO, 2022; UN HLEG, 2022). Third, we offer a detailed comparison of publicly available methods and illustrate the divergence of assessment outcomes using a global company example. Fourth, we examine how methodological decisions impact the delivery of comprehensive, detailed, transparent and timely LCTS assessments at scale. Our findings help policymakers navigate methodological variations in transition assessments and determine disclosure regulation scope.

2. Literature review

This article is situated within the growing research on the methodological choices related to corporate LCTS assessment initiatives. Much of this work has examined the methodological choices of alignment with low-carbon pathways, a forward-looking metric that translates corporate climate targets into projected temperature outcomes known as implied temperature rise (ITR) or alignment (de Franco et al., 2023; FOEN, 2022; GFANZ, 2022; Haalebos & Fouret, 2022; Noels & Jachnik, 2022; Portfolio Alignment Team, 2020, 2021). However, as these assessments are mainly used by investors, who are often able to access paywalled data. This neglects the use of transition strategy assessments by other actors within the governance landscape. Consequently, it is crucial to extend comparative analysis beyond traditional ESG evaluations and purely ITR-focussed metrics. To this end, this study comprehensively compares the approaches of independent assessment initiatives.

Several studies reveal common methodological features. Noels and Jachnik (2022) examined 16 anonymised methodologies for climate-alignment assessment from commercial services providers, research institutes or civil society organizations. Their study reveals differences in methodological design across four key dimensions: (1) the type of GHG performance metrics, (2) the temporal perspective and coverage, (3) the types and scopes of greenhouse gases considered and (4) the treatment of offsets and avoided emissions. Analysing five initiatives' publicly or privately shared data, they show a divergence in medium- and long-term ITR scores across eight emissions-intensive sectors. The authors also examine how alignment across different scores is linked to methodological differences. For example, they find that methodologies' allowance of offsets influences whether companies' ITR scores are aligned within the sample data. To address these divergences, they advocate for users of transition strategy data to look beyond GHG emission-based metrics and use a dashboard of indicators, including other robustness indicators. We build on this finding and recommendation to explore how additional transition components beyond GHG emissions reporting are assessed and focus on publicly available assessments to enable non-anonymized insights.

Raynaud et al. (2020) identified four key methodological steps across 11 approaches used to generate ITRs. Raynaud et al. (2024) expanded the technical review to more than 50 different methods, revealing a growing range of assessment techniques from public and private sources. The study argued that differences in 'systemically important methodological choices' originate from varying views on what decarbonization pathway alignment means in the real economy. Additionally, they contend that the complexity and multitude of methodological design choices make it highly challenging to identify the underlying causes of rating variations and assess the sensitivity of results to these choices. Similarly, Chmel et al. (2023) found substantial disagreements in climate ratings across six assessments of 3,208 companies. However, their study focussed on company-level variables such as size or location as drivers of different ratings, rather than methodological differences. The authors highlighted that the opacity of many assessment methodologies created a 'black box' effect, hindering transparency. Finally, Rekker et al. (2021) found inconsistencies across three corporate climate rating initiatives commonly used in academic studies, cautioning that the differences hinder stakeholders in making informed decisions on whether companies are aligned with global carbon budgets.

To address the challenge of more transparency on methodologies, other studies have focussed on specific components of transition strategies, such as emissions target integrity (Faria & Labutong, 2019; Papadopoulos, 2022), or data inputs used in assessments. For instance, Busch et al. (2022) examined inconsistencies in corporate carbon performance data used across major ESG data providers. They found high consistency for scope 1 emissions data but significant discrepancies in scope 2 and 3 reporting. The authors recommend that users of emissions data be aware of these inconsistencies and advise companies and investors to contribute to improving carbon performance data accuracy. Bendig et al. (2025) further examine carbon performance data, revealing a trade-off between accuracy and availability. Their findings show that although third-party verified data is the most accurate, it is also the least accessible.

In summary, the literature has provided an understanding of methodological diversity and design choices. However, there has been neither a systematic synthesis of methodological choices across publicly available assessments nor an examination of how key transition components, developed within the landscape of voluntary corporate climate action standards, are incorporated into these methods (Becker et al., 2024). This gap

motivates our study, which compares ten LCTS assessment initiatives to understand methodological design, coverage of transition strategy components, and implications for policy and governance.

3. Data and methods

3.1. Selection of assessment initiatives

We sought to examine assessment initiatives, which (i) assess companies' transition strategies or their components with a public methodology, (ii) are not one-off exercises but intend to inform stakeholders regularly based on the latest information, (iii) cover multiple sectors and countries and (iv) make results publicly available. To identify relevant initiatives, we reviewed and collected actors related to producing knowledge on corporate low-carbon transition strategies from English-language studies published before 1 July 2024 (Becker et al., 2024; Binger et al., 2023; Noels and Jachnik, 2022; Raynaud et al., 2020, 2024). From these studies, we compiled 82 actors (see Supplementary Material: S1). Of these, 10 met our criteria for assessment initiatives (shown in Table 1). While the assessment initiatives' differing objectives and focus areas likely

Table 1. Categorisation and naming conventions of low-carbon transition strategy (LCTS) assessment initiatives and organisations.

Assessment initiatives and their description	Methodology referenced
Independent assessments	
LobbyMap: '... maintains the world's leading database on corporate and industry association climate policy engagement, with metrics and profiles covering 600 companies and 250 industry associations.' (InfluenceMap, 2024a)	(InfluenceMap, 2024b)
MSCI Net-Zero Tracker (MSCI-NZ): '... indicates the collective progress of the world's listed companies toward curing climate risk. The report, which highlights companies' alignment with global climate goals [is] based on a series of indicators [...]' (MSCI Inc, 2025)	(MSCI ESG Research LLC, 2024)
Net Zero Tracker (NZT): '... is about transparency and accountability. We are the only independent tool that provides a comprehensive view of net zero across all nations and the world's largest regions, cities, and companies.' (Net Zero Tracker, 2024a)	(Net Zero Tracker, 2024b)
Corporate Climate Responsibility Monitor (CCRM): '... analyses the climate strategies of 51 major global companies, critically assessing the extent to which they demonstrate corporate climate leadership.' (NewClimate Institute, 2024b)	(NewClimate Institute, 2024a)
Planet Tracker: '... identifies the companies causing the worst environmental and social damage within targeted supply chains, then identifies the investors and lenders in these companies whose financing is enabling these practices to continue unchallenged.' (Planet Tracker, 2025)	(Planet Tracker, 2024)
Transition Pathway Initiative (TPI): '... intends to be a key part of the post-COP26 financial infrastructure to drive greater transparency and accountability for corporate commitments to net zero and to support those seeking to raise capital in public markets' (Transition Pathway Initiative, 2025)	(Transition Pathway Initiative, 2023)
WBA Climate and Energy Benchmark: '... assesses the highest corporate carbon emitters. It measures their progress against the Paris Agreement [...] [It] covers rankings of 450 of the world's most influential, keystone companies in high-emitting sectors' (World Benchmarking Alliance, 2025)	(World Benchmarking Alliance, ADEME and CDP Worldwide, 2023)
Independent validations	
SBTi Corporate Net Zero Standard (CNZS): '... is the world's only framework for corporate net-zero target setting in line with climate science. It includes the guidance, criteria, and recommendations companies need to set science-based net-zero targets consistent with limiting global temperature rise to 1.5°C.' (Science Based Targets Initiative, 2025)	(SBTi, 2024; Science Based Targets initiative Services Limited, 2024a, 2024b)
Composite assessments	
Climate Action 100+: '... is an investor-led initiative to ensure the world's largest corporate greenhouse gas emitters take appropriate action on climate change in order to mitigate financial risk and to maximize the long-term value of assets.' (Climate Action 100+, 2025)	(Climate Action 100+, 2023)
TransitionArc Beta: '... is a one-stop tool to assess corporate transitions and unlock finance at speed and at scale needed to meet climate goals. For the first time in the public domain, the best available analysis of corporate climate transitions has been brought together in one place' (Climate Arc, 2024)	(Climate Arc, 2024)

¹At the time of the data collection cut-off, the MSCI-NZ assessment results were publicly accessible on MSCI's website; however, as of December 2025, these are no longer available.

influence their methodologies, their shared goal of evaluating corporate transition strategies still allows for important comparative findings.

These ten assessment initiatives can be categorized into three types with distinctive functions (Figure S-1 in the Supplementary Material: S2):

- **Independent assessments** are based on their own or publicly available standards, guidance or methods.
- **Independent validations** undertake assessments that involve additional assurance of a corporation's transition strategy based on a company's request and may use non-public data.
- **Composite assessments** display, compile and/or interpret data from other assessments, enhancing indicator coverage or highlighting differences in outcomes.

3.2. Two-part analytical framework

We developed a two-part framework to review and compare assessments systematically. Part I of our framework examines the overall assessment setup. Drawing on key characteristics identified in existing studies (Becker et al., 2024; Bingler et al., 2023; Noels and Jachnik, 2022; Raynaud et al., 2020, 2024), our assessment covers the following nine criteria: assessment type, headline outcome metric, methodological modality, data sources, companies assessed, sector coverage, availability of sector-specific methodologies, connection to other assessment initiatives and the frequency and format of release. Detailed explanation of these criteria and the corresponding results are provided in Supplementary Material: S3.

Part II of our framework examines the transition strategy components covered by the methodology (Table 2). We narrowed down 10 relevant components based on their representation of different critical aspects of transition planning, as identified by mapping and extracting criteria from policy-relevant guidance documents (ISO, 2022; UN HLEG, 2022). These documents were chosen because they represent the outcomes of expert and practitioner consensus processes, making them particularly relevant for policy applications. While there is emerging research that attempts to identify statistically significant explanatory variables that are correlated with corporate emissions reductions, suggesting that some transition strategy components may be more indicative of implementation than others (e.g. Bolay et al., 2024), this study does not set out to evaluate the relative importance of the components.

Table 2. Transition strategy components examined.

Component category	Component	Explanation and significance
Targets	GHG mitigation targets	Science-aligned short-, medium-, and long-term targets provide evidence of a company's decarbonization trajectory.
Transition plan	Emission reduction measures	Emission reduction measures demonstrate whether a company is planning or implementing targeted actions that address major sources of emissions.
	Approach to unabated and residual emissions	Understanding a company's treatment of unabated and residual emissions offers insight into the legitimacy of a company's overall transition plan.
	Value chain engagement approach	A company's value chain engagement shows how a company works with suppliers and customers to reduce emissions beyond its direct operations.
	Capital expenditure	Capital expenditure data can indicate whether a company's investments in its future assets align with its emissions reduction goals.
Progress tracking	Just transition planning	Evidence of just transition planning shows whether a company is ensuring fair and equitable transitions for stakeholders affected directly by its climate actions.
	Emissions reporting	Annual emission disclosures across the value chain provide an overview of a company's emission profile and changes thereof over time.
	Emission reduction progress	Measurements of progress on emission reductions reflect a company's performance over time.
Governance	Board oversight	Governance measures aligned with climate goals reflect whether corporate leadership and management are effectively supporting the company's transition planning and execution.
External engagement	Lobbying and policy engagement	A company's lobbying activities related to climate policy reveal whether a company is supporting or undermining its climate commitments within the broader policy environment.

To systematically analyse how different assessments approach these components, we examine three key aspects: which components are used by different assessments, how the components are analysed, and how they are weighted in the overall evaluation. We developed a transparency typology to code the analysis of each component, noting the percentage weighting or component significance where available:

- (a) **Disclosure check** – Tracks whether a company discloses specific transition strategy components in public and/or non-public sources. Disclosure checks may help users track companies' current climate performance and hold them accountable to their forward-looking ambitions (Bowman & Wiseman, 2020), but they alone do not provide clear insights and recommendations on how a company's LCTS align with climate goals (Rekker et al., 2021).
Example: Whether the company discloses low-carbon capital expenditure, presented as 'Yes/No' or share of total annual capital expenditure.
- (b) **Context-limited assessment** – Compares transition strategy components to defined decarbonization benchmarks, pathways and/or other quantitative or qualitative criteria. Context-limited assessments are derived from additional analysis of disclosed information, such as modelling, but they provide little transparency about the reasoning behind their conclusions on a case-by-case basis. No further publicly available case-specific assessment details are provided, making the results non-replicable.
Example: Assessing low-carbon capital expenditure using 1.5°C-compatible benchmarks or criteria, but with no further details such as data, calculations or assumptions underpinning the assessment.
- (c) **Contextualized assessment** – Compares transition strategy components to defined decarbonization benchmarks, pathways and/or other quantitative or qualitative criteria. Provides publicly available case-specific assessment details, making results replicable as all assumptions and data are clearly communicated. Contextualized assessments offer users additional insights by providing company-specific evaluations.
Example: Assessing low-carbon capital expenditure using 1.5°C-compatible benchmarks or criteria, with clear communication on data, calculations or assumptions underpinning the assessment.
- (d) **Unclear approach** – Limited or no explanation of the assessment method.

We specifically distinguish between 'context-limited' and 'contextualized' assessments to obtain insights into how the LCTS assessment initiatives apply their methodologies and the degree of accountability each assessment initiative has against the companies that are assessed. Contextualized assessments offer users additional insights and information on company-specific evaluations, for example, providing additional explanations on data inputs and considerations alongside a GHG emission reduction target assessment. By these means, they might be especially useful for stakeholders influencing companies directly through advocacy or engagement or for researchers and analysts trying to replicate the assessments. 'Context-limited' assessments, however, do not imply in any way that they are of lower assessment quality or rigour than 'contextualized' assessments.

To reduce subjectivity in qualitative coding, we used dual-author review. Additionally, draft findings were shared with assessment initiatives, with a 90% response rate, and revised using publicly available or publishable information. The coded data and indicator weightings are provided in Supplementary Materials (S5 and S6, respectively).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Part I: assessment setup

The ten assessment setups differ significantly across key features (Table S-3 in Supplementary Material: S4).

4.1.1. Methodological modality and outcome metrics

Seven initiatives produce aggregated ratings or index scores. Planet Tracker, CNZS and TransitionArc use various criteria to rate whether a company is or is not aligned with a specific temperature pathway. The outcome of LobbyMap's analysis is presented through a 6-point rating (from 'A' to 'F'), while CCRM uses a 5-point scale (from 'High' to 'Very Poor'), and WBA assigns a total numerical index score, composed of many

sub-ratings. Two assessment initiatives use modelling as their main modality to indicate whether a company's strategy aligns with certain global warming thresholds, expressed through an implied temperature rise (e.g. alignment with a 1.5°C pathway). TPI (CP) and MSCI-NZ use projected emissions data and targets to determine alignment with many temperature scenarios. Two initiatives (CA100+ and NZT) use multi-criteria frameworks to evaluate various climate-related metrics without an overarching score.

Notably, each initiative employs its own methodology, rather than following external standards or guidelines. However, some organizations outside the scope of this analysis adopt external standards. For example, Climate Integrity applies the HLEG recommendations to assess ten Australian headquartered companies (UTS Institute for Sustainable Futures, 2024).

4.1.2. Company and sector coverage

The total company coverage ranges from tens to several thousands, with some assessment initiatives also repeating the analysis of companies. Sector coverage ranges from four to twenty, though sector categorization was determined by the initiatives and not standardized. Four initiatives use sector-specific methodologies (SBTi, TPI (CP), TransitionArc, WBA). Five others use a common methodology with sector-specific adjustments, such as different sectoral benchmarks in certain parts of the assessment (CA100+, LobbyMap, MSCI-NZ, CCRM, Planet Tracker). Two initiatives (TPI (MQ) and NZT) apply a uniform approach without sector-specific adjustments, as they focus on high-level components through disclosure assessments (explained further in section 4.2) that do not vary significantly by sector.

4.1.3. Frequency of assessments and release format

Assessment frequency ranges from weekly individual updates (e.g. LobbyMap uses weekly scanning to update ratings) to annual or less frequent sector-based batches (e.g. CA100+, TPI). Therefore, differences in headline outcomes can result from initiatives relying on data captured at different times. Since companies release their sustainability and annual reports at various points throughout the year, two same assessments with different data cut-off dates may yield different results.

4.2. Part II: assessment of transition strategy components

The ten assessments vary significantly in their coverage of transition strategy components, assessment approach and weighting assigned to each component (Figure 1; initiative-specific results in Table 3; See Supplementary Materials S5 and S6 for coding results).

4.2.1. Component coverage

GHG mitigation targets are the most covered components, as nine initiatives analyse short- and/or long-term targets. Eight initiatives include GHG mitigation targets as one of multiple components (CCRM, TransitionArc, NZT, CNZS, Planet Tracker, and WBA). Emissions reduction measures, lobbying and policy engagement are the second most analysed components. Five initiatives assess approaches to unabated and residual emissions, of which only one is a contextualized assessment. The contextualized assessment provides company-specific insights into the volume of offsets planned and the types of projects they will support. Just transition planning is covered by the fewest initiatives. In our sample, the WBA covers the most components, assessing eight out of ten. While a variation in an assessment's focus, such as LobbyMap's specific emphasis on lobbying, is a contributing factor to differences in component coverage, it does not fully explain the lack of coverage for certain components across all assessments (e.g. CNZS). Emissions progress receives sparse coverage ($n = 4$), requiring more attention as transition planning matures in the coming years.

4.2.2. Assessment approach

Four initiatives exclusively conduct contextualized assessments providing company-specific information across all components they examine (CCRM, LobbyMap, Planet Tracker, WBA). Two initiatives apply a mixed approach using context-limited assessments for GHG mitigation targets and disclosure checks for other components (CA100+, TPI). TPI derives two separate ratings: an implied temperature alignment based on a context-

Figure 1. Count of approaches by transition strategy components across ten initiatives.

limited assessment of GHG mitigation targets and a management quality score based on a disclosure check of company information on several other components, such as historical emissions and emission reduction measures. NZT exclusively provides a disclosure check, while MSCI-NZ covers the single component of GHG mitigation targets in a context-limited assessment. CNZS provides context-limited assessments for all components it covers, meaning it does not offer company-specific insights on how specific expectations for GHG mitigation targets have been met.

4.2.3. Weighting factor

Across all initiatives, no clear trend can be identified in certain components having more weight than others. Two initiatives use sector-specific component weightings (TransitionArc, WBA) while two others use the same component weighting across different sectors (CCRM, Planet Tracker). TransitionArc suggests default weightings but also allows users to customize them according to their priorities. Five initiatives do not apply any weighting as they either do not aggregate component-specific ratings into a headline outcome (CA100+, NZT), or they derive a headline outcome from a single component (MSCI, LobbyMap, CNZS). TPI's management quality (MQ) score, based on a disclosure check, does not assign specific weights to individual components. Instead, it uses a levels approach, with criteria becoming progressively more challenging across five levels. A company is considered to have reached a specific level only if it meets all the criteria for that level, as well as those for all preceding levels.

4.3. Illustrative case study

We present the comparative assessment results of Toyota Motor Corporation (hereafter Toyota) to examine practical differences (Figure 2). Toyota was selected as a case study due to its coverage by most initiatives ($n = 9$).

Headline outcomes vary significantly across assessments. TPI (MQ) evaluates Toyota's climate change management through numerous indicators, performing strongly, rating it at Level 4 out of 5, the second-highest tier

Table 3. Comparison of rating initiatives' transition strategy components, methodological approaches and weighting. n/a: not applicable.

		CA100+	LobbyMap	MSCI-NZ	NZT	CCRM	Planet Tracker	CNZS	TransitionArc	TPI	WBA
Component category	Component	Composite assessment	Independent assessment	Independent assessment	Independent assessment	Independent assessment	Independent assessment	Independent validation	Composite assessment	Independent assessment	Independent assessment
Targets	GHG mitigation targets	Context-limited assessment (Weight: n/a)	-	Context-limited assessment (Weight: 100%)	Disclosure check (Weight: n/a)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 25%)	Contextualized assessment for 2030 (Weight: 6.25%)	Context-limited assessment on-demand (Weight: 100%)	Contextualized or Context-limited assessment (Weight: 15-35%, sector-specific and adjustable by user)	Disclosure check and Context-limited assessment (Weight: Level 4 of 5, 100% for ITR)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 15% of ACT assessment)
	Emission reduction measures	Disclosure check (Weight: n/a)	-	-	Disclosure check (Weight: n/a)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 25%)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 12.5%)	-	-	Disclosure check (Weight: Level 3 of 5)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: Unclear as combination of different elements, sector-specific)
Transition planning	Approach to unabated and residual emissions	Disclosure check (Weight: n/a)	-	-	Disclosure check (Weight: n/a)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 25%)	-	Context-limited assessment (as part of GHG mitigation targets)	-	Disclosure check (Weight: Level 5 of 5)	-
	Value chain engagement approach	-	-	-	-	Unclear approach (Weight: unclear, part of Emission reduction measures)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 10%)	Disclosure assessment (No weighing, optional addition to GHG mitigation targets)	-	-	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 0-20% of ACT assessment for suppliers and customers each, sector-specific)
	Capital expenditure	Disclosure check and Context-limited assessment (Weight: n/a)	-	-	-	-	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 12.5%)	-	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 15-35%, sector-specific and adjustable by user)	Disclosure check (Weight: Level 5 of 5)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 0-40% of ACT assessment, sector-specific)
	Just transition planning	Disclosure check (Weight: n/a)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 20% of total assessment)
Progress tracking	Emissions reporting	-	-	-	-	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 25%)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 6.25%)	Context-limited assessment (as part of GHG mitigation targets)	-	Disclosure check (Weight: Level 3 of 5)	-
	Emissions progress	Context-limited assessment (Weight: n/a)	-	-	-	-	-	-	Contextualized or Context-limited assessment (Weight: 20-45%, sector-specific and adjustable by user)	-	Contextualized assessment (Weight: Unclear % of ACT assessment, sector-specific)
Governance	Board oversight	Disclosure check (Weight: n/a)	-	-	-	-	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 10%)	-	Disclosure check or Contextualized assessment (Weight: 10-15%, sector-specific and adjustable by user)	Disclosure check (Weight: Level 4 of 5)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 10-12% of ACT assessment)
External engagement	Lobbying and policy engagement	Disclosure check and Context-limited assessment (Weight: n/a)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 100%)	-	-	-	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 5%)	-	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 5-10%, sector-specific and adjustable by user)	Disclosure check (Weight: Level 5 of 5)	Contextualized assessment (Weight: 2-8% of ACT assessment, sector-specific)

in its framework. TPI (CP), CNZS and MSCI-NZ rate Toyota's emission reduction targets as aligned with a 2.0°C pathway or better. Notably, these assessments focus on GHG reduction targets rather than Toyota's overall transition strategy. However, they analyse emissions through different lenses. TPI evaluates the CO₂ performance of new cars (downstream scope 3) by 2050 and rates it as 1.5°C-aligned, average new vehicle emissions (grams of CO₂ per kilometre (WLTP)).

SBTi's CNZS only rates near-term (2030 and 2035) targets. It assesses Toyota's absolute scope 1 and 2 GHG emissions reduction target (68% by 2035 from a 2019 baseline) as aligned with a 1.5°C trajectory, and its scope 3 targets for passenger light-duty and light commercial vehicles (33.3% reduction per vehicle km by 2030) as aligned with a well-below 2°C scenario. As both TPI and CNZS use context-limited methodologies, they do not provide company-specific evaluations, such as the base year emissions data examined, reducing the replicability of their findings. For the SBTi CNZS, its access to non-public (and sensitive) information provided by companies is likely one of the reasons it cannot publicly substantiate its validation results.

In contrast, CCRM, TransitionArc and WBA rate Toyota's overall transition strategy as not aligned with global climate goals. All three assessments derive their outcomes from aggregate evaluations of multiple components. CCRM's contextualized assessment covers Toyota's entire value chain GHG reduction targets (including upstream scope 3 emissions), as well as specific emissions reduction such as the 1.5°C-aligned ICE phase-out timeline. This inclusion impacts the overall rating. WBA, which covers the most transition indicators, reaches similar conclusions.

Some initiatives show alignment in component-specific ratings. TPI and CA100+ produce similar results since TPI serves as the data provider for CA100+'s disclosure framework. There is also broad agreement

Toyota Motor Corporation										
	CA100+ ¹	LobbyMap	MSCI-NZ	NZT	CCRM	Planet Tracker ²	CNZS	TransitionArc ³	TPI ⁴	WBA
Headline outcome	No headline outcome	D	2.0°C	No headline outcome	Integrity: Very poor	Does not assess the company	1.5°C <small>(Near-term scope 1+2) Well below 2°C <small>(Near-term scope 3)</small></small>	E	Management quality: Level 4 Carbon performance for 2050: 1.5°C	Total score: 43.6/100
Publication date	October 2024	Q4 2024	Unclear <small>(retrieved on 27.11.2024)</small>	September 2024	April 2024	n/a	November 2022	Unclear (retrieved on 11.11.2024)	MC: May 2023 CP: June 2024	November 2021
Targets	Net Zero: Yes Long term: Yes Medium-term: Partial Short-term: Partial		2.0°C <small>(Weight: 100%)</small>	Disclosure tracked	Very poor <small>(Weight: 25%)</small>		Near-term: 1.5°C & well below 2°C Long-term: n/a	C <small>(Weight: 15%)</small>	2027: National pledges 2035: Below 2°C 2050: 1.5°C	2 out of 3 <small>(Weight: 15%)</small>
	Partial, meets some criteria			Disclosure tracked	Very poor <small>(Weight: 25%)</small>				Disclosure tracked	0.9 out of 7 0.6 out of 1.8 <small>(Weight: Unclear)</small>
	No, does not meet criteria			Disclosure tracked	Very poor <small>(Weight: 25%)</small>		Not transparent how this criterion was evaluated for Toyota		Disclosure tracked	
Transition planning	Value chain engagement approach				Outcome unclear <small>(Weight: unclear, part of Emission reduction measures)</small>		Not chosen as an optional target			0.3 out of 1.2 0.3 out of 0.8 <small>(Weight: 5%)</small>
	Capital expenditure								Disclosure tracked	0.4 out of 0.4 1.2 out of 2.4 <small>(Weight: Unclear)</small>
	Just transition planning	No, does not meet criteria						E <small>(Weight: 35%)</small>		Not assessed for automotive manufacturers
Progress tracking	Emissions reporting				Poor <small>(Weight: 25%)</small>		Not transparent how this criterion was evaluated for Toyota		Disclosure tracked	
	Emission reduction progress	Partial, meets some criteria								Unclear
Governance	Board oversight	Partial, meets some criteria								
	Lobbying and policy engagement	Partial, meets some criteria							Disclosure tracked	1.5 out of 2.2 <small>(Weight: 10%)</small>
External engagement		Partial, meets some criteria							Disclosure tracked	0.1 out of 1.2 <small>(Weight: 5%)</small>

1 CA100+ presents multiple assessment outcome for some components. Here we present its disclosure framework, rather than its alignment assessment, as it is the default presented data.
 2 Planet Tracker only assesses companies within the of Chemicals and Food & Agriculture sectors.
 3 TransitionArc offers multiple assessment outcomes, depending on the data input selection by the user. Here the default assessment result is presented.
 4 TPI presents two different assessment outcomes, with differing assessment approaches. Both are presented here as they cover different components

Figure 2. Comparison of assessment outcomes across ten initiatives for Toyota Motor Corporation (assessment from November 2024). The cells' background colours reflect the actual colour coding applied by each assessment initiative. In the absence of any colour coding by the initiative, we leave the cell's background blank.

among assessments evaluating emissions progress, board oversight and lobbying and policy engagement. For instance, on board oversight, WBA assigns Toyota a score of 1.5 out of 2.2, indicating moderate to low performance. CA100+ and TransitionArc also issue low ratings, highlighting governance concerns.

When comparing headline outcomes, assessment timing is a factor to consider, as some evaluations reflect older or more recent data. However, in this case, variations are driven more by differences in methodological choices rather than timing, as Toyota did not significantly change its targets.

Overall, Toyota's case underscores the complexities of comparing different methodologies on transition strategies: differences in data, assessed components, and underlying assumptions can lead to widely varying conclusions. These differences can lead, as in the case for Toyota, to high variance in assessment outcomes both at the individual component level (e.g. GHG mitigation targets) and overall outcomes presented as the headline summary of a given assessment. This variance becomes particularly problematic if context-limited assessments – providing limited transparency on case-specific assessment details – cannot be independently reviewed or replicated by users. This points to a general need to better track and facilitate harmonization of methods towards transparent and robust assessments.

4.4. Trade-offs between assessment breadth, approach, and frequency

Table 4 synthesizes findings from Part II of the analysis into three dimensions relevant to the policy challenge of scaling high-quality assessment practices: breadth, component-level assessment approach and frequency. No initiative provides comprehensive, current, contextualized evaluations for over 1,000 companies, which we refer to as an indicative number of companies that cover the large majority of the global economy (as in S&P 500 and Forbes 2000) and GHG emissions, either as direct emitters, value chain emitters or their financiers. Assessment initiatives that cover a wide range of components with contextualized assessments tend to do so for a smaller number of companies (CCRM, Planet Tracker). WBA assesses many components and companies in great level of substantiation but less frequently.

LobbyMap, in contrast, focuses on a single component but does so with a great level of substantiation and across many companies. Others, like MSCI-NZ and CNZS, assess many companies frequently but with limited context for the assessment result or component coverage. CA100+ covers many components but does so with disclosure checks only. In contrast, the NZT provides frequent updates across many companies but does so only through disclosure checks. Trade-offs between breadth, component-level assessment, and frequency are likely influenced by various factors, including resource constraints, theories of change of each assessment initiative, as well as differing methodological focuses. It is also worth highlighting that only one assessment initiative in our analysis provides a contextualized analysis of offsetting. This is surprising

Table 4. Differences in component-level assessment approach, breadth and frequency across the ten assessment initiatives.

Assessment initiative	Component-level assessment approach			Breadth		Frequency
	● Contextualized	● Context-limited	● Disclosure	Components covered	Number of companies	Publishing occurrence
				● 8–10 ● 4–7 ● 1–3	● > 1000 ● 100–1000 ● <100	● Weekly ● Monthly to annually ● More than annually
CA100+			●	●	●	●
LobbyMap	●			●	●	●
MSCI-NZ		●		●	●	●
NZT		●		●	●	●
CCRM	●			●	●	●
Planet Tracker	●			●	●	●
CNZS		●		●	●	N/A
TransitionArc ¹		●		●	●	●
TPI ²		MQ ● CP ●		●	MQ ● CP ●	●
WBA				●	●	●

¹TransitionArc offers multiple ratings. For 'depth', the average of the default assessment approach was used.

²TPI presents two different ratings, with differing assessment approaches and the number of companies assessed. Both are presented here.

because offsetting has long been one of the most contentious issues in the GHG mitigation action effectiveness discussions; the importance of careful consideration of offsetting has been highlighted as good practice by several standard-setting bodies, including the ISO (2022), the UN High-Level Expert Group on the Net-Zero Emissions Commitments of Non-State Entities (UN HLEG, 2022) and the Assessing Companies Transition Plans Collective (ATP-Col, 2024).

In this regard, TransitionArc, as a composite assessment initiative, stands out by achieving a relatively good balance of breadth, component-level assessment approach and frequency. It allows users to examine and compare individual components, such as lobbying, which LobbyMap covers extensively, across assessment initiatives. Here, we observe an emerging, innovative approach to overcome the aforementioned trade-offs as well as to provide a platform on which multiple independent assessment initiatives could collaborate.

5. Conclusion and recommendations

Assessment initiatives shaped corporate climate governance by (i) innovating and experimenting with standards, guidelines and assessment methods, (ii) introducing validation mechanisms such as the CNZS for GHG mitigation targets and (iii) delivering analyses for litigation and other uses (Hale, 2024). These initiatives currently fill a critical governance gap in corporate climate accountability, which is rapidly evolving and likely to remain relevant amidst political uncertainty. This study advances the understanding of methodological diversity in voluntary corporate LCTS assessments for users and policymakers seeking to design effective accountability regulations. Our findings of varying coverage, weighting, and assessment approaches across ten different initiatives offer valuable insights for policymakers and assessment initiatives. For example, criteria such as the companies' approach to residual emissions, board oversight and consideration of just transition were found to be covered by considerably fewer assessments. Despite the contributions of the assessment initiatives, we emphasize the need to improve transparency, consistency, and comparability.

In the absence of universal standards, enhanced dialogue among LCTS assessment initiatives would improve understanding of assessment approaches, limitations and alignment with standards. However, we appreciate that there are situations in which policymakers and other assessment users need to take immediate action to hold companies accountable, based on potentially conflicting assessments, to ensure, e.g., effective implementation of their national climate change mitigation policies. In such cases, we recommend that the assessment users first study the assessments that (i) cover the LCTS components they consider to be most important or relevant for them and (ii) conduct contextualized assessments.

5.1. Towards enhanced methodological transparency and harmonization

Our comparison across a multitude of parameters demonstrates that assessments exhibit a trade-off between their breadth, component-level assessment approach and frequency. This raises a critical policy question: How can policymakers support assessments that deliver comprehensive, detailed, transparent and timely assessments of companies' transition strategies at scale? Addressing this need is essential for policymakers, regulators, investors, civil society and researchers, who depend on clear, comparable and up-to-date evidence to support regulatory integration, transition plan validation, investment decision-making and corporate accountability aligned with 1.5°C-consistent pathways.

Composite assessments like TransitionArc and CA100+ provide one forward-looking approach to how methodological diversity can be harnessed constructively. We identify several potentially effective mechanisms in their operations: (i) cross-referencing different methodological components to identify reasons for assessment outcome variation, (ii) enhancing assessment quality by leveraging individual initiatives' strengths in specific components, (iii) expanding coverage by integrating well-substantiated evaluations across different transition strategy elements and (iv) providing starting points for resolving substantive differences between assessments.

We also conclude that analysts and researchers on corporate climate action need to put more focus on how the assessment methodologies are applied in specific assessment initiatives. The community has made significant progress on developing more robust standards and guidelines (ISO, 2022; SBTi, 2025a; UN HLEG, 2022), but our research on 10 selected initiatives has shown that there is limited transparency on their methodologies' coverage and assessment approaches.

The advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) could also significantly boost our ability to assess companies' climate strategies (Bingler et al., 2022; Senni et al., 2025). However, currently available generative AI tools are found to be limited in factual accuracy when used for assessing climate pledges and identifying potential loopholes (Hsu et al., 2024).

5.2. Role of voluntary assessment initiatives in supporting policymaking

Looking ahead, emerging regulatory frameworks may begin to address the governance of corporate climate knowledge currently managed by independent initiatives. Discussions around the European Union's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD) have initiated requirements for mandatory transparency in corporate transition planning (European Commission, 2024). However, regulatory rollback risks and uneven global regulatory development mean that assessment initiatives will continue playing essential roles in informing a wide range of users on the state of corporate climate action in the near term.

Beyond understanding methodological diversity, policymakers require clear access to assessment methodologies to effectively integrate them into regulatory frameworks. Our research process revealed significant transparency challenges: direct communication with the initiatives was often necessary to clarify aspects such as under which methodological section or indicator-specific transition components were covered. To ease user understanding, initiatives could provide clearer public documentation, including data sources and specifying assessed targets. Voluntary assessment initiatives could play a larger role in informing regulatory processes by contributing methodologies and expertise, including guidance for auditors interpreting alignment with 1.5°C pathways in jurisdictions with emerging audited transition plan requirements.

To support regulators and other users, we propose a centralized repository of corporate LCTS assessment methodologies, established and administered by an independent governance body. This repository could track and facilitate the harmonization of methods, promoting transparent and robust assessments aligned with policy developments (NewClimate Institute, 2024a, 2024b, 2024c). Its reporting and comparison framework could draw on the analytical framework presented in this paper, as well as ongoing efforts in global LCTS governance guidance (ISO, 2022; UN HLEG, 2022). Additionally, the repository could help users understand how specific LCTS initiatives align with and are interoperable with global or regional climate disclosure frameworks such as the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) or the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG). Finally, the repository could serve as a platform for assessment initiatives to connect, share approaches, recognize their unique strengths, reduce duplicated efforts and converge towards emerging good practices.

We find such a repository feasible because some relevant efforts are already underway. The European Union (EU) is pioneering this approach for commercial ESG providers; new legislation starting in 2026 will require them to disclose more information on methods and data sources to operate within the EU (European Council, 2024). Based on the information submitted to a centralized repository, regulators can also produce guidance on how to consistently report on methodologies, increasing standardization and easing method integration into regulation (Hale, 2021). Organizations such as ISO, United Nations agencies or a consortium of universities, could independently administer the repository.

Researchers also have an important role to play. Beyond continuing to examine the rigour and quality of LCTS assessment methods (Berg et al., 2022), they can also engage proactively with assessment initiatives and regulators to refine methodologies and develop ways to scale assessments of high rigour to large sets of companies. Besides the initiatives (partly) operated by academic institutions (e.g. TPI, NZT), there are currently not many initiatives other than SBTi that specifically invite scientists to guide methodology and assessment development processes (SBTi, 2025b).

5.3. Areas for future research

This study has a number of methodological limitations. First, the study only covers developments up to mid-July 2024, limiting insight into this fast-evolving field. For example, the TransitionArc platform is in beta version, and SBTi is revising its CNZS (Science Based Targets initiative, 2025). Updated guidances, such as the Greenhouse Gas Protocol (Greenhouse Gas Protocol, 2024) and the ISO's Net Zero Standard (ISO, 2024), are expected in the coming years, which could reshape reporting and assessment practices. Future research could capture these developments and whether assessments align with external standards.

Second, excluding paywalled initiatives limits the analysis, as their data is widely used. Future studies could explore these providers' approaches to corporate climate assessments. The disclosure of methodologies and data used by the ESG rating providers, as spearheaded by the EU, followed by the realization of our proposed central repository of LCTS assessment methodologies and data, could significantly enhance researchers' access. Similarly, this study's exclusive focus on English-language literature may have omitted relevant assessments conducted in other languages. Broader searches are encouraged in future research.

Third, although sector-specific methodology components were noted, this study did not compare differences in sectoral data or approaches in detail. For example, to assess target alignment in the automobile sector, WBA evaluates fleet emissions reduction targets based on absolute emissions, whereas TPI uses emissions intensity calculations measured in CO₂ per km (see TransitionArc, 2025). Future research could build on this study to explore the differences in sectoral methods.

Fourth, details of the institutional design for the proposed corporate LCTS assessment methodology repository are outside the scope of the research presented in this article. However, these details need to be explored for operationalization. Future research could explore design elements such as the repository's governance, organizational structure, independence, funding, conflict-of-interest policies and version control.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT 4.0 in the late stage of the process to edit the language of the article. After using the tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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